

SITE GPR	YEAR 10	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.2946 Max: 63.3454	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1179 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropoc	
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In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 604 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION
gravel layer below cocciopesto (1178) in Room 1

Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1178	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
			Compaction	Color
			<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1178	Covers: 1180
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
Excavated with pick
A 182 - Ivory hair pin

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: South central
Shape: irregular patch preserved

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions): level surface below flat cocciopesto

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope)

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): Fairly uniform thickness of a few cm between cocciopesto surface above and crushed tufo layer below

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations:

= walls 1184

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Gravel preparation layer for coccio pesto floor surface in Room 1. Truncated in the rest of the room, along with floor surface itself and other preparation layers.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by *S. Rous*

on *15.07.10*

Revised by *CHH*

on *19.7.2010*

PDFd by *JGM*

on *21.07.2010*

Entered by

on